

Citizen science and eDNA: an innovative approach to studying biodiversity.

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Le laboratoire LIENSs est une Unité Mixte de Recherche interdisciplinaire (UMRi 7266 La Rochelle Université – CNRS). LIENSs met l'interdisciplinarité au service des enjeux du développement durable en lien avec le littoral. Il intègre les compétences de nombreuses disciplines qui vont des sciences de l'environnement aux sciences humaines en passant par la chimie et les biotechnologies. Ses recherches se focalisent tout particulièrement sur le fonctionnement du système littoral, son évolution dans un contexte de changement global et d'urbanisation croissante des côtes, son usage et son exploitation durable.

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Introduction

Over the past century, human activities have caused climate change that is affecting every ecosystem, both terrestrial and aquatic (Butchart *et al.*, 2010). The erosion of biodiversity is a major concern for our societies, and the general public is increasingly aware of the need to protect biodiversity. Citizens are getting more involved every day in their efforts to protect our planet's biological wealth, and in the past decades the field of citizen sciences (CS) has grown. We can go back to 1900, at the very beginning of the National Audubon Society's annual Christmas bird count to find the first citizen scientists (Cohn, 2008). This project is the first large-scale known involving citizen scientists, it has occurred at the end of each year since the first edition. This program has begun thanks to Frank M. Chapman, an ornithologist concerned about declining bird populations and few passionate about birds. They started counting birds across North America each year, and today there are tens of thousands of volunteers collecting data on birds. The first steps toward CS had been made, since then it has never stopped evolving. CS have been common in the scientific world since the 1960's but they have been clearly mentioned in scientific articles from only the end of the 1990's. Ever since, CS has developed, and saw a significant increase in scientific papers since 2010 (Kullenberg & Kasperowski, 2016). Haklay *et al.*, (2021) highlight the plurality and diversity of interpretation when it comes to CS. They insist on the importance of context specificity regarding the definition of CS. In this review, we will consider CS in environmental and ecological sciences as a partnership between non-professional and professional of the field and/or in the lab aiming to collect and/or analyze data (Haklay *et al.*, 2021 ; Fraisl *et al.*, 2022; Kullenberg & Kasperowski, 2016 ; Schneider *et al.*, 2017). According to Kullenberg and Kasperowski (2016), CS are most common in environmental sciences and ecology. A need for large-scale studies in those fields can explain the rise for citizen assistance to do field work to acquire more data ((Luzar *et al.*, 2011). One example of large-scale (and large space) biodiversity monitoring has been introduced by the Museum of Natural History of Paris and the French Office of Biodiversity in 1989. They created VIGIENATURE, a program based on CS with scientific and political purpose. This program does not focus on one species but on several like birds, butterflies, pollinating insects, bats, snails, or more wild urban plants. All the knowledge acquired with this program followed strict scientific protocol and allowed scientists to access field data to better understand consequences of global changes on biodiversity. The most important concern on CS is about results quality, mostly related to the training citizens received beforehand the collect of

data. Taking the example of studies aiming at sustainable development goals of the UN using CS, (de Sherbinin *et al.*, 2021) highlight the quality of citizen work, when well trained. This demonstration is consistent with a large majority of studies using CS data that are convinced of the great quality of data collected by citizen scientists (Crall *et al.*, 2011), but also with the obvious increasing use of CS in scientific studies.

Parallely, technological development has permitted environmental and ecological studies at scales never envisioned until recently. In the field of genetics in particular, the development of DNA amplification using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) or next generation sequencing (NGS) techniques has fostered the rise of new DNA technique (Hebert *et al.*, 2003) developed DNA barcoding which consists in identifying one taxon by sequencing a standardized DNA fragment. Then metabarcoding which allows the simultaneous identification of several species followed shortly after. The development of metabarcoding and improvement in laboratory technologies have led to the development of environmental DNA (eDNA). As species interact with their environment, they will expel DNA around, this DNA will then stay in the environment and will be more or less preserved (Thomsen & Willerslev, 2015). Thereafter, it is possible to collect a sample of the environment and thanks to laboratory technology on DNA amplification such as PCR it is possible to know which species were in this habitat. First used in the 1980's in marine slough and brackish water, eDNA has gained in interest ever since (Ogram *et al.*, 1987). The methods allow an efficient extraction and isolation of high-quality DNA in every type of ecosystem, all it takes is a sample from the habitat (air, water, soil...). Studies using eDNA can have several purposes, from the biodiversity inventory to target an invasive species, and can be applied to every type of habitat. Development of eDNA brought a brand-new look on ecological studies, enabling us to see the invisible. Thomsen and Willerslev (2014) emphasize the achievement of eDNA in terms of knowledge on bacterial diversity, and more broadly on microorganisms, in every type of environment. Beyond the world of invisible, eDNA also allows it to be less invasive on the field while collecting samples, thus enabling better detection of species that can be difficult to distinguish at some life stage, such as juvenile amphibians (Dejean *et al.*, 2012). Indeed, eDNA sensitivity can be better to detect some species than traditional detection methods (Thomsen and Willerslev, 2015). It also enables us to have an overview of spatial distribution of species when conducting larger-scale studies. It is clear that eDNA will see a lot of improvement in the years to come, but it is already a revolutionizing tool for gene-based biodiversity discovery and biomonitoring (Baird & Hajibabaei, 2012).

The approach of combining CS and eDNA to optimize the scale of ecological monitoring is on the rise. CS which has focused on large (or at least visible) species can now reach the sub-microscopic species using eDNA techniques (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Several biotechnology companies are developing toolkits that allow citizens to take an active part in eDNA samples collection. We can cite for instance SPYGEN, a French company that offers ready-to-use toolkits reachable by anyone, including citizens, by following a strict protocol. This collaboration between scientists and citizens enables large-scale study at lower cost and takes an active part to change the public's perception of biodiversity (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Even if CS and eDNA seem to be two complementary tools, the use of both in the same study is recent. This review seeks to give an overview of the state of use of CS and eDNA in studies based on the scientific literature. Our aim is to emphasize how CS and eDNA are used together in scientific studies and the spatial and temporal trend of such sampling approaches in ecological sciences.

Material and methods

In order to conduct a relevant review, we followed a common literature review methodology used by Cabioch & Robert, 2022; Dupont *et al.*, (2020). The first step was to identify and extract relevant papers using the appropriate keywords on Scopus and Google Scholar (1). Then we had to select the most pertinent papers among the found ones to have a persuasive data set (2). Finally, we classified and analyzed each paper (3).

2.1. Examination of Scopus and Google Scholar

We used two data-bases Scopus and Google Scholar, each of these databases were explored in April 2023. We chose to not restrict the publication date of articles. To determine which articles will be included in our review we first had to define relevant keywords to have the best query. The term “eDNA” was chosen as a contract form of environmental DNA; every article uses eDNA to refer to it. To have references using CS we chose to use “citizen” and “participatory” as keywords. We started with a broad search to not miss any article and conduct a non-exhaustive review. The main database used was Scopus, in which we searched [“eDNA” AND “citizen”] and [“eDNA” AND “participatory”]. We completed this database with Google Scholar in which we used the same keywords to ensure we did not miss any paper. This first

step of identification was composed of 138 papers. Once all papers downloaded on Zotero, we transferred them on an Excel sheet. We used a spreadsheet function which enabled us to delete all the duplications, we then had a data set of 132 papers.

2.2. Removal of irrelevant papers and inclusion of exclusion criteria

After paper selection, we had to remove irrelevant ones. We went from 132 to 40 articles after reading title and abstract using the following criteria:

- a) Exclusion of articles with only one of the two main keywords (i.e., only “eDNA” or “citizen/participatory”), $n = 68$. Since the aim of our paper is to review the use of eDNA in CS, the use of only one of these two concepts in the abstract was eliminatory. For some papers a more precise analysis of the text was required to be sure not to remove a relevant paper. Some papers' aim was to develop eDNA sampling techniques for an easier use of CS. In these studies, CS were not used directly but papers were considered relevant for our review.
- b) Exclusion of papers remote to the ecological field (e.g., history, medical sciences), $n = 9$. Indeed, CS and eDNA are also used in a very different way in the medical field among others.
- c) Exclusion of paper using neither eDNA nor CS, $n = 15$. No mention of CS or eDNA in the title/abstract/keywords of the paper. A rapid overview was conducted and if no mention of these words were made in the whole paper or only in the last part of the discussion, the paper was considered irrelevant for our review.

At the end of this step, we removed 92 papers, and remained with 40 papers as data for our review, then we could continue a more detailed analysis.

2.3. Classification of references

In order to apply a relevant classification, we read every article and fill in the following field: i) ecosystem type (freshwater, marine, terrestrial), ii) geographical zone, iii) aim of the study, iv) role of citizen, v) citizen type, vi) funding of the study. All the fields were beforehand divided in subcategories. For the first category we determine three types of subcategories

matching the three big types of ecosystems: freshwater, marine and terrestrial to have a first overview of what type of ecosystems was most studied. For the sake of accuracy, we subdivided these three types of ecosystems into sub ecosystems (river, estuary, coastal, port, beaches, soil, pond...) The geographical zone was subdivided in two subcategories: 1) country of the main institution leading the study and 2) countries where samples were collected. This classification was chosen to determine where eDNA and CS are the most used and see if any trend appeared. For the aim of the study, we chose to split articles into four different subcategories: 1) study with a specific target species, 2) study with a specific invasive target species, 3) study providing an overview of biodiversity in an area and 4) study participating to research and development in terms of eDNA technology or CS. The role of citizen is an important category, we made four different subcategories: 1) citizen as field technician (collect, analysis of samples), 2) citizen supporting role in eDNA (observation, monitoring), 3) citizen end-user (research and development for eDNA), and 4) funding citizens. For the category citizen type, since citizens needed to volunteer to be part of studies, we distinguished students from the field of study from children or adults with no direct link with the institution leading the study. Finally, for the funding type, we distinguish public from private funding and in each type of funding we determine if the fund came from local, regional, national, or international scale.

Results

3.1. Time and space distribution

One of the first things that stood out from identified papers is their recent publication date. All of them were published from 2015, this highlighted the recent concern about this topic in the literature, and the development of techniques that made citizens' involvement possible. The first publication was from Biggs *et al.* (2015), it seemed to be the forerunner of eDNA and CS in scientific literature. Since then, the number of yearly publications has increased (Figure 1).

Figure 1 : Trend in the number of scientific publications by ecosystem type since 2015.

It was also interesting to note their geographical distribution. Here are the results regarding the country of the main institution leading the study, sorted by continent: Oceania was the one with the lowest number of papers published ($n=4$), then Asia ($n=5$), North and South America ($n=13$) and Europe ($n=18$). Inside continents, there was a lot of disparity regarding the country of publication. Asia is a continent with more than 45 countries, among them only 4 (China, Indonesia, Japan, and Cambodia) published papers related to eDNA and citizen sciences. In America, publications were dominated by the USA, which was the only American country in our review. In Europe, 7 countries published papers on this subject, but Denmark and UK gathered more than 50% of those. When it came to countries where samples were collected, a total of 24 countries were represented. The Figure 2 one showed the repartition of publication per type of ecosystem and per country. Important inequality of publication but also participation to study CS/eDNA came out of this map, it clearly showed the lack of studies in Africa, South Asia and South America.

Figure 2 : Spatial distribution of sampling sites. Each circle represents one study and the color the ecosystem type.

3.2. Type of ecosystem

When we explored closer the content of the articles, it was possible to identify several types of ecosystems: freshwater, marine and terrestrial. It appeared that 11 papers concerned terrestrial ecosystems, 19 papers focused on freshwater ecosystems and 23 about the marine ecosystem. If freshwater took a bigger place at the early stage of eDNA and citizen science, it was the marine ecosystem that prevailed in this type of study. The total number of papers was bigger than our identified database because several papers ($n=8$) treat several types of ecosystems. 57.5% of identified articles are focused on marine ecosystems, we then identified sub-type of ecosystems: beaches, port, estuary, dock, jetty, coastal, and open sea. It appears that 5 focused on port. The two other types of ecosystems did not show such a diversity in their sampling environment. In comparison with the spatial distribution, Figure 2 showed that 4 countries out of the 24 where samples were collected have worked on terrestrial ecosystems.

3.3. Purpose of studies

Regarding the target species of studies, 9 articles focused on a specific taxon other than invasive species, it represented 22% of identified articles. 10 studies were focused on invasive species. 10 studies provided an overview of biodiversity thanks to eDNA. The last category, research, and development for eDNA and CS represented slightly more articles, as there were 11 studies among the identified studies. When it came to comparing results of the type of ecosystems and the aim of the study, Figure 2 showed that each aim is present in each ecosystem. There was no clear trend in the relation between ecosystem type and aim of the study.

3.4. Role and type of citizen

In our identified papers, 16 of them used citizens as field technicians. When compared to ecosystem type, among these 16 studies, 6 were in terrestrial ecosystems, freshwater and marine ecosystems both represented 5 studies. In seven of those studies, citizens were volunteers from conservation organizations near the sample area. In six studies, the citizens implied were students (high-school or college students) from local schools (Figure 3.a.) or university, most of the time they did not just collect samples, they also helped to analyze data from the field (Figure 3.b.). The rest of the studies involved ordinary citizens that volunteered or citizens with specific skills (boat license, owner of a boat). At last, studies using citizens as field technicians aimed to have an overview of biodiversity ($n=7$) or target a specific non-invasive species ($n=7$) in large majority. Only one of these studies focused on research and development.

a.

b.

Figure 3 : a. Children scientists assisting a researcher during eDNA samples collection in a port in Corsica (Photo by H. Thomas, project QUAMPO) ; b. Highschool students analyzing eDNA samples in the lab after collecting them on the field in Denmark (Photo by A.P. Schultz).

Papers also used citizens as supporting roles in an eDNA study, this represents 7 of our identified articles. Among these studies, 3 focused on freshwater, 3 on marine and 1 on terrestrial ecosystems. Citizens were involved as observers on the field, warning of the presence/absence of a specific species, or even as eradicator of an invasive species. This kind of role increased the participation of professional citizens (i.e., fisherman warning about a species of fish). In this category we also chose to put a study using passenger ferries to collect samples at sea. Citizens took no direct part in the study but without them this study could not have been created, it seemed essential to highlight the passive role of citizens in that case.

At last, 17 studies involved citizens as end users, that means that citizens had no direct involvement in studies, but they are one of the motivations. Among these studies, 10 had an aim of research and development in eDNA technology at large scale. The rest of studies aimed to detect invasive species ($n=6$) or got an overview of biodiversity ($n=1$). Every study in this category highlighted the important role of CS in science programs in the future and the fact that collaboration between citizens and scientists is for the great majority of studies beneficial for each side. We chose to do a fourth category of citizens: citizens financially involved in the studies. This category only included one study among our selection, but it seemed interesting to us to highlight that through crowdfunding, citizens can get involved by choosing to finance certain types of studies.

3.5. Funding

Regarding the funding of studies, most papers were funded by public organizations ($n=25$). Among those, 36% aimed at research and development ($n=9$) and 32% targeted a specific invasive species ($n=8$). Public organizations were often working on a national scale ($n=14$), or were related to universities funding the studies. When it came to citizens' role in study funding by national organizations, in most of them citizens were end users ($n=12$) and field technicians ($n=9$). It also appears that every geographical zone used public funding, there was no trend appearing regarding a country favoring one funding source over another.

On the other hand, the 16 articles funded by private organizations, mostly focused on overviewing biodiversity ($n=7$) and targeted a specific non-invasive species ($n=5$). Looking closer at the citizen role in private funded study, it appeared that in most of them citizens were field technicians ($n=7$), then end users ($n=5$) and at last have a supporting role ($n=4$). On the aim side, private funding studies were more focused on overviewing biodiversity ($n=7$) and

target a specific non-invasive species ($n=5$) than on invasive species ($n=2$) and research and development ($n=2$).

Discussion

We chose to do this review using Scopus and Google Scholar. These two major databases specialized in transdisciplinary scientific publication enabled us to get a certain number of papers when searching keywords “eDNA” and “citizen science”. We chose not to search for other keywords such as “participatory”, “public” because based on our previous research, citizen science is clearly the most common term (Eitzel *et al.*, 2017). Being a recent trend, we expected to find fewer articles, many eDNA/CS sampling campaigns being on going and their results not published. For instance, UNESCO launched a program (Enhancing climate Services for Improved Water Management) which involved citizens from local communities, with this program local knowledge is promoted in combination with scientific data. To this day, this program is not the subject of any scientific paper. This example is one among others that does not appear in our research for scientific literature, for most of them it is actions led by an NGO or association (i.e., WWF Hong Kong, Greenpeace or more the European Citizen Science Association). It would have been interesting to include gray literature, but this proved challenging in practice. We also chose to keep papers not dealing directly with citizens, i.e., studies using citizens as end users and not as an active part of their method. This choice was made following the assumption that studies designed to improve the use of eDNA by citizen scientists were helping future studies and were relevant to our review.

Looking closer at countries where CS and eDNA were used in scientific studies it was clear that it was in the USA that most of the studies took place. It can be interesting to link the number of publications to the total population of the country. The World Bank took a census of over 331 million of inhabitants in the USA in 2021, which makes the country the third most populated in the world (UN). According to Nature Index, the USA is the second most publisher country per year, just behind China. Compared to money put into research of these two countries, the USA invests 2.73% of the GDP each year, when it is 2.05% of the GDP for China (UNESCO). These numbers are among the most important in the world, in terms of dollars it is the USA that invests more in scientific research (OECD). Therefore, our results with the USA as the world leader in studies using eDNA and CS is not surprising. However, China is the most

densely populated country of the world and one of the largest, the use of CS would be an interesting way to develop eDNA studies. In our review, the USA published mostly about the terrestrial ecosystem. This made us point out that our review was unsurprisingly biased towards countries invested the most in research and ecosystems located in their territory: e.g., countries with no access to the sea have no interest in developing research on the marine ecosystem. The main American program in our review was the CALeDNA, it aimed to monitor Californian biodiversity by pairing CS and Californian researchers in collecting eDNA from soil samples. This program openly shared its results to show the potential of eDNA for conservation purposes. In CALeDNA the use of CS was very useful to sample at large-scale, in that case at the California state scale. Our results also showed that if researchers came from one country, they did not always restrict samples to one country. Six studies in our database sampled in several countries (including the one associated with their main institution). CS and eDNA studies are not worldwide spread, such disparity could be explained by the difference among the investment in scientific research in each country and the fact that eDNA is a relatively new technology that requires advanced laboratory technologies.

Regarding the classification, ecosystem types were divided into three categories (marine, freshwater and terrestrial), which represent the three big types of ecosystems. To have a more specific overview we decided to do sub ecosystem types, since we could not find this information in every paper we decided to not analyze too much. Our review showed that CS and eDNA are more and more used in marine ecosystems than in terrestrial or freshwater. These results raise questions, is water easier to sample? Are marine ecosystems more reachable than others? According to Sandahl & Tøttrup, (2020) marine citizen sciences is more and more developed since 2014, even though they review not only eDNA studies, we can assume that eDNA/CS studies follow the same trend. One of the possible explanations could be that marine ecosystems are eDNA's and CS's poor relation and today we assist to the catch up of science with this ecosystem. If we look closer to the sub ecosystem type, 5 studies took place in ports. Ports seem to be an attractive area to lead eDNA/CS study. Indeed, they are by definition easily reachable, and port ecological problems are numerous. Lapinski *et al.*, (2014), highlighted that microhabitat are created by anthropic structures in ports, Ports are at the interface between terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, they go through invasive species problematic (Keller *et al.*, 2011), but also pollution due to fuel, terrestrial contaminant supply or even noise pollution (Omubo-Pepple *et al.*, 2010). They are also a place where microhabitat can develop (Lapinski *et al.*, 2014), they are very rich ecosystems. Hence eDNA study in port seems more than

relevant, furthermore citizens could be easily involved in such studies. QUAMPO is a pioneer French program in this field, they bio-monitored the ecological state of three ports in Corsica and did an ecological inventory of fish biodiversity using citizen sciences and eDNA. This initiative shows the importance and interest of ports in such studies, especially to monitor invasive species (Madon *et al.*, 2023) Their results show that using citizens (children in that case) to collect eDNA samples is relevant and allows to raise awareness of citizens (O'Neil *et al.*, 2020). Hence, marine ecosystems, and particularly ports, seem to be a habitat lending itself to the use of eDNA and CS. Beyond the harbors, some urban areas are also very accessible and would allow the development of ecological studies involving CS and eDNA. Already practiced in several urban areas (Charvoz *et al.*, 2021; Marizzi *et al.*, 2018; McCaffrey, s. d.), the use of genetic technology (DNA barcoding) and/or CS shows good results, while eDNA could provide more precise data and could enable more appropriate management policy.

The unequal repartition between the different roles that citizens can have in studies, could reflect the fact that there is still a lot to improve in CS using eDNA, given that a bit more than one quarter of our papers aimed to develop research and development in this field. This can be explained by the relatively recent start of the combination of these two means to collect data for a scientific purpose. However, every study in this review that had a direct use of citizens (both field technicians and with a supporting role in eDNA) showed very good results in terms of sampling quality. This concurs with what was already present in the literature with the use of CS for other purposes (Crall *et al.*, 2011). If CS enables sampling at a larger scale for fewer costs, every study reviewed underlined the necessity of good training and above all a good motivation for volunteers. This study showed that most citizens involved in scientific research are already concerned about ecological issues. Wehn *et al.* (2021) insist on the necessity to clearly explain the expected impact of the study and every study in this review highlights the major importance of a good communication between scientists and citizens. The quality of collected data relies on the motivation and the diligence of each sampler. Citizens that know exactly the aim of the study and understand the importance of a strict protocol will be more careful in collecting samples (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Beyond the large-scale collection of samples, another strength of CS in scientific studies is the infusion in society of biodiversity knowledge. Compton *et al.* (2020), place that mobilizing citizens enables rapid responses to disturbance and early detection of invasions. Indeed, involving citizen scientists creates connections to the natural world and people gain sensitivity for local species. Hence, we can assume that the rise of awareness in the public community will speed up establishment of conservation measures.

The participation of students and conservation association volunteers reflects a bias in the very definition of CS. Volunteers for such studies are already aware of the importance of biodiversity conservation, and therefore do not represent society. While citizen participation must of course remain voluntary, it would be interesting to target communities with little or no awareness. This could lead to a better infusion of knowledge into society and reveal the true power of CSs. This reflection is linked with the lack of studies in several parts of the world, thus Luzar *et al.* (2011) conduct a study in Guyana using local communities' knowledge and volunteering. These citizens had specific and precise knowledge about the field that was very useful to researchers, the socioecological aim of this study led to a real implication of communities and gave quality results. Thus, the involvement of all sections of society has produced results that are more than satisfactory for scientific research. Once again, the quality of samples and analyses carried out by citizens depends on their motivation and involvement in the project (Fraisl *et al.*, 2022). It also shows that CSs are an interesting tool for developing studies and data on biodiversity in countries that haven't yet taken the plunge. This also raises the question of the difference between field professionals and non-professionals in terms of sampling skills and the data quality and robustness that can be expected for the data to be analyzed and lead to reliable results and conclusions. Can a passionate ornithologist who has been observing birds for years be considered a citizen like any other? Hence, the environmental background of citizens has a major role, especially regarding data collection quality. If we take an example of bird observation study, a citizen that has a hankering for ornithology will provide more reliable data during the observation than a random citizen with no knowledge beforehand. Being able to provide reliable, robust data through CS projects is a major challenge and requires rigorous and relevant field sampling protocols and training from the scientists to the citizens. Poor data quality is one of the biggest drawbacks of CS, using citizens who are already familiar with field work can guarantee a better data quality.

Between direct citizen involvement in the study and funding, one study stood out for citizen financing of the study. Based on crowdfunding, this study witnesses another role that citizens can have in science. Wheat *et al.* (2013) highlight the difficulties that crowdfunding can lead to, the necessity to reach a large crowd is often the limit of this type of funding. It requests an important implication from researchers to bring the study visibility, Sauermann *et al.* (2019) underline that crowdfunding is mostly used by junior scientists. Surprisingly there is no relation between the topic of the study and the success of crowdfunding campaign (Wheat *et al.*, 2013). As it is demonstrated by the authors, the real opportunity of crowdfunding lies in

reaching citizen sensitivity at the very beginning of their project and then gaining visibility. This special relation between citizens and researchers contribute to forge stronger confident links between the public and scientific sphere. It's not only a way of financing part of the study, but above all it's a way of raising public awareness of ecological causes. Researchers have a duty of transparency that breaks down the barriers between non-specialists and specialists. Regarding the other funding sources, private funding seems to favor citizens from conservation organizations or professionals, while public funding more readily involves students and members of the public. This phenomenon could be explained by the more direct relationship between researchers and students in the public sector. Public universities are meeting places for these two communities and encourage interaction. As a result, researchers in the public sector would favor the citizens close to them. That is, of course, if the study does not require very precise knowledge of the chosen field.

Conclusion

This review provided an overview of the role of citizens in the development of innovative biodiversity monitoring tools such as eDNA. Based on our research, it is highly likely that CS will develop even further in the years to come. It is a fantastic opportunity for scientists around the world to obtain data on a large spatial and temporal scale. The local knowledge of the public is also a source of information for scientists, enabling them to identify areas to prioritize when it comes to biodiversity conservation. Extensive data collection enables the determination of biodiversity indicators, following a strict protocol of course; quantity must not neglect quality (Couvet *et al.*, 2008). eDNA and CS are two complementary tools can be used to raise awareness of ecological issues and enable the development of more in-depth studies to ensure effective environmental management. Given current concerns about environmental impact, CS takes a rather a low-tech approach especially compared to the current trend in high-tech monitoring tools in ecology (sensor networks, remote sensing...).

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Abstract

The development of citizen science and environmental DNA (eDNA) in recent years has brought many benefits to the scientific community. This review seeks to give an overview of studies using both citizen science and eDNA based on scientific literature. Our aim is to emphasize how citizen sciences and eDNA are used together in scientific studies and the spatial and temporal trend of such sampling approaches in ecological sciences. Using Scopus and Google Scholar we found that the first use of both methods in scientific literature was in 2015, and this combination has not stopped increasing ever since. Studies are conducted in every ecosystem but not at a global scale. Citizen science and eDNA together serve many purposes, from targeting an invasive species to the biodiversity inventory. Citizens from several horizons take part in studies using eDNA, not always with the same role (from field technician to end user). This review highlighted the power tool that citizen science and eDNA together could represent for the future of science. If citizen science has been long used in scientific studies, this review puts a new light on the great opportunities that it can bring to the scientific world when associating them with eDNA. Those are two complementary tools able to raise awareness of ecological issues and enable the development of more in-depth studies to ensure effective environmental management.

Key-word: Citizen science; eDNA ; biodiversity ; terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems ; environmental management ; biomonitoring.